

EXAMINATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA USE IN NEWS DISSEMINATION BY MEMBERS OF SELECTED TERTIARY INSTITUTION IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study examined the use of social media on news dissemination within Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, focusing on the extent of usage, its impact on news spread and the types of news most frequently shared. The study was anchored on the Diffusion of Innovations Theory. The design for this study was the survey research design with a population of 47,485 from which a sample of 400 respondents was selected. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire administered to staff and students of the selected universities. The findings reveal that members of the Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use social media to a considerable extent for news dissemination with a mean score of 3.7, although it is not regarded as the primary channel of communication. The results further indicate that social media has a significant impact on the spread of news with mean scores of 3.1, enhancing its speed and reach within the institutions. In terms of content, local news, entertainment news and community events are most frequently shared with mean scores of 3.8, 3.2 and 3.1 respectively, while sports news receives comparatively less attention. This pattern reflects a communication culture that prioritizes institution-specific information and socially engaging content over other categories. In conclusion, the findings indicate the growing importance of social media as a complementary and influential tool in institutional news dissemination. The study therefore contributes to a clearer understanding of how digital communication dynamics shape information flow within cosmopolitan university communities in Rivers State and highlights the need for strategic management of social media to ensure accuracy, credibility and effective engagement. It also shows the complementary and amplificatory role of social media within institutional communication systems. Based on these findings, it is recommended that Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education should maintain verified and actively managed social media accounts to ensure accurate, timely and credible dissemination of news while reducing misinformation. Also, the school authorities should link their social media pages directly with other traditional communication channels such as official websites, emails and notice boards to maximize reach and maintain reliability. Furthermore, regular digital literacy programs should be organized to educate students and staff on ethical news sharing, source verification and responsible use of social media.

Keywords: social media, news dissemination, community news, localized community, institution.

Introduction

In the era of characterized high social media usage, the methods by which people acquire news have undergone a substantial transformation. This change is characterized by a notable transition from conventional media platforms to digital and social media formats, which offer more participation, greater interactivity, and easy accessibility. This transformation has not only had an effect on the physical features of news distribution but has fundamentally transformed how individuals participate in, comprehend, and engage with news material. Among the countless digital channels that are accessible, social networking platforms has emerged as a powerful tool for disseminating news, riveting worldwide audience, including immense number of university students (Marco, 2005 cited by Roy & Roy, 2024).

The aftermath of the prevalence of these social media platforms in daily life is the blurring of distinctions between social interaction and the consumption of news. More intriguingly, while these platforms act as instruments for social networking, they also serve as key sources of news and information (Roy & Roy, 2024). This integration of news content into social media feeds creates a one-of-a-kind set of dynamics that have impacted public awareness, the formation of opinions, and the overall consumption of news. As social networking platforms are becoming more influential in public conversations, it is crucial to comprehend the patterns and reasons behind the news consumption on social networking platforms (Ceccagnoli, et al. 2012).

Social media's rapid flow of information, coupled with its interactive nature, empowers users not only to consume but also to share, comment on, and influence the spread of news stories. This dual role of consumers and disseminators underscores the significance of assessing the frequency of news consumption and investigating the underlying motivations driving these behaviors. To comprehend the broader implications of news literacy and to fight against disinformation, it is crucial to grasp knowledge of these motives. Such motives may stem from convenience, personal inclination for social networking platforms over traditional news, or situational exposure (Guess et al., 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The rapid proliferation of social media platforms has significantly transformed the processes of news production, dissemination and consumption within contemporary societies. In cosmopolitan institutions such as universities, polytechnics and other higher educational establishments, social media has become a dominant channel through which information is circulated among students, staff, and external stakeholders. Platforms such as X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp now serve not only as spaces for interpersonal interaction but also as critical hubs for breaking news, institutional announcements, advocacy, and opinion formation. While this shift has expanded access to information, it has also intensified the assertive nature of communication, characterized by immediacy, emotional expression, opinionated framing, and rapid amplification of content.

Despite the advantages of speed and participatory engagement, the assertiveness embedded in social media communication raises concerns about credibility, verification, agenda-setting, and the potential distortion of institutional narratives. In cosmopolitan environments like those found in Rivers State, where institutions accommodate diverse cultural, ethnic and ideological backgrounds; the assertive tone and user-driven dissemination of news may shape perceptions in ways that either enhance transparency or exacerbate misinformation and conflict. The speed at which news spreads on social media often outpaces traditional verification mechanisms, creating an environment where unverified or sensational content may gain legitimacy through repetition and engagement metrics.

Furthermore, although existing scholarship has examined social media's influence on journalism and public discourse, limited empirical attention has been given to how *assertiveness* in social media communication specifically affects news dissemination within institutional settings in Rivers State. There is insufficient understanding of whether social media assertiveness strengthens participatory information sharing, undermines institutional authority, influences audience trust, or alters the framing and reception of news within these cosmopolitan institutions. The contextual realities of Rivers State; marked by political sensitivity, youth activism, and digital engagement, make this inquiry particularly relevant.

Consequently, the problem this study seeks to address is the lack of empirical evidence on the extent to which social media assertiveness shapes the dissemination, credibility, and reception of news within cosmopolitan institutions in Rivers State. Without such understanding, institutional administrators, communication practitioners, and policymakers may be ill-equipped to design effective communication strategies that balance openness, responsibility, and accuracy in the digital age.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Find out the extent of social media usage among members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education for news dissemination.
2. Examine the impact of social media on the spread of news within the select schools.
3. Identify the types of news most frequently shared on social media platforms by members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. To what extent do members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use social media for news dissemination?
2. How does social media impact the spread of news within the select school?
3. What types of news are most frequently shared on social media platforms by members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education?

Scope of the Study

This study focuses on examining the influence of social media assertiveness on news dissemination within selected cosmopolitan institutions in Rivers State. The research is geographically limited to Rivers State and institutionally confined to higher education institutions characterized by cultural, ethnic, and social diversity, such as Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The study specifically investigates how assertive communication patterns on social media platforms affect the circulation, framing, credibility, and reception of news within these institutional environments.

Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory, developed by Everett Rogers in 1962, explains how new ideas and technologies spread through a social system. According to Rogers, diffusion is the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the participants in a social system (Rogers, 2003). This theory has been widely applied in

various fields, including healthcare, education, and marketing, to understand how innovations are adopted and spread.

The diffusion process is influenced by several key elements, including the innovation itself, communication channels, the social system, and time. The innovation can be an idea, practice, or object perceived as new by an individual or unit of adoption (Rogers, 2003). Communication channels, such as mass media or interpersonal communication, play a crucial role in transmitting information about the innovation from one person to another. The social system, comprising interrelated units working together to solve problems, also affects the diffusion process.

Rogers identifies five adopter categories that describe the sequence in which individuals adopt innovations (Rogers, 2003). Innovators, who make up about 2.5% of the population, are adventurous and cosmopolitan, and they are the first to adopt new ideas. Early adopters, comprising about 13.5% of the population, are opinion leaders who are integrated into the social network and adopt innovations early. The early majority, making up about 34% of the population, are deliberate followers who adopt innovations after careful consideration. The late majority, also comprising about 34% of the population, are skeptics who adopt innovations only after a majority has endorsed them. Finally, laggards, who make up about 16% of the population, are traditional and isolated individuals who are the last to adopt innovations.

The rate of adoption is influenced by several factors, including the perceived relative advantage of the innovation, its compatibility with existing values and experiences, its complexity, trialability, and observability (Rogers, 2003). For example, if an innovation is perceived as having a significant relative advantage over existing solutions, it is more likely to be adopted quickly. Similarly, if an innovation is compatible with existing values and experiences, it will be more easily adopted. On the other hand, if an innovation is complex and difficult to understand, its adoption may be slowed.

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory has been applied in various contexts to promote the adoption of new ideas and technologies. For instance, in the field of healthcare, the theory has been used to understand the adoption of new medical technologies and practices (Greenhalgh et al., 2004). In education, the theory has been applied to study the adoption of new teaching methods and technologies (Surry & Ely, 2007). In marketing, the theory has been used to understand the diffusion of new products and services (Mahajan et al., 2000). One of the key implications of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory is that innovators and change agents can develop targeted strategies to promote the adoption of innovations. For example, they can use mass media to reach a wider audience and interpersonal communication to build relationships with opinion leaders (Rogers, 2003). They can also design innovations that are compatible with existing values and experiences, and provide opportunities for trial and observation.

Despite its wide application, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory has faced criticisms, including concerns about pro-innovation bias and individual-blame bias (Rogers, 2003). Pro-innovation bias refers to the assumption that innovations are inherently good and should be adopted by everyone. Individual-blame bias refers to the tendency to blame individuals for their failure to adopt innovations, rather than considering the role of the social system and other external factors.

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory provides a valuable framework for understanding how new ideas and technologies spread through a social system. By recognizing the factors that influence adoption and the characteristics of different adopter categories, innovators and change agents can develop targeted strategies to promote the diffusion of innovations. While

the theory has its limitations, it remains a widely used and influential theory in the field of innovation and technology adoption. According to the theory, diffusion is the process by which an innovation or idea is communicated through certain channels over time among members of a social system. In this context, social media can be considered the innovation, and Polytechnic community platforms serve as the channels through which news is circulated.

Literature Review

Evolution of News Consumption

The transition of news consumption from its traditional roots to the contemporary digital landscape marks a significant evolution in the dissemination and reception of news. Historically, news was disseminated through print and broadcast media, with newspapers, radio, and television playing pivotal roles in keeping the public informed on a daily basis (Fenton, 2009). These traditional platforms were characterised by their one-way communication flow, where information was procured by journalists and consumed by the audience with limited interaction between the two (Klinger & Svensson, 2015).

The digital transformation was marked by the rise of online news portals and the proliferation of digital devices, enabling consumers convenient access to news content anytime and anywhere (Wolf & Anna, 2014). The integration of social media platforms into the news ecosystem represented a further evolution, transforming not just the manner in which the news is consumed but also how it is disseminated and deliberated upon. Social media has democratised news distribution, allowing not only limited to professional journalists but on contrary ordinary users to contribute to the news cycle. As an outcome, an increasingly participatory culture has emerged, where news consumers are actively involved in curating, sharing, and commenting on news content (Newman, 2009).

The transition has significant ramifications that affect the dynamics of news production, dissemination, including consumption pattern. The news landscape has become dispersed considering the journalists and news organizations are no longer the traditional gatekeepers of information. Furthermore, the immediacy and accessibility of news on social media platforms have fostered an environment where news is more than just information; it's a catalyst for social interaction and engagement (Newman, 2009). The abundance of news sources and the ease of sharing information on social media have contributed to issues such as information overload, misinformation, and the erosion of public trust in news media. These challenges underscore the need for continued research into news consumption behaviours and strategies to enhance media literacy in the digital age (Lee & Kim 2017).

A paradigm change in the dynamic between news producers and consumers has occurred with the evolution of news consumption from traditional to digital platforms, with the emergence of social media as the pinnacle. This transformation has democratised news dissemination, facilitated greater interaction and engagement, and presented new challenges that shape the current and future landscape of news consumption (Posetti & Matthews, 2018).

Social Media as a News Source

In the landscape of news consumption, a momentous transition is marked by the ascendance of social media as a primary source of news, reflecting broader changes in communication technologies and societal habits. With their vast networks and user-generated content, social media has become integral to the way people discover, consume, and share news (Anna & Henrik, 2011). The framework for this shift is the unique attributes of social media, such as its immediacy, interaction, and ability to spread information rapidly. According to research, a significant portion of the population now relies on social media for news due to the ease with

which they can access a variety of sources and viewpoints within their social networks. Key players in this ecosystem include platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), WhatsApp, and Instagram, each facilitating distinct modes of news engagement and distribution. For instance, Facebook and X have become spaces where news is often encountered incidentally as users engage with their social feeds (Molyneux & Coddington, 2020).

The consumer's exposure to the diverse information and their engagement with different viewpoints has profound implications by this incidental exposure to news on social media. (Molyneux & Coddington, 2020) While some scholars posit that social media can increase exposure to a wider array of news sources, others caution against the potential for echo chambers, where users are primarily exposed to information that reinforces their existing beliefs (Garrett, 2009).

A crucial area of research is on the role of algorithms in curating news content on social media platforms. Algorithms shape the news agenda by prioritizing certain types of content over others, which inevitably effects what news is seen and also how it is perceived by audiences. This curation express concern on the equilibrium between tailor made content and the need for exposure to a broad spectrum of news (Van Duyn, & Collier, 2021). The flawless dissemination of news on these platforms combined with the lack of traditional editorial constraints has facilitated to the swift proliferation of false or deceptive information.

Motivations for News Consumption on Social Media

The motivations driving individuals to consume news on social media are multifaceted and deeply interwoven with the social and psychological fabric of digital interactions (Roy & Roy, 2024). This complexity underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of why people turn to social media platforms for news, moving beyond convenience to explore the underlying psychological, social, and contextual factors. The motivations for news consumption on social media are varied and encompass various cognitive and social factors. According to Donghee and Mousa (2019), a primary motivation is the convenience and rapid access to news. People use mobile devices and social media platforms to quickly get updates from a variety of sources, often in real-time.

Low cognitive effort can be another reason why users digest micro-news, which are brief updates often accompanied by links to full articles. This ease of consumption makes it more likely for users to engage in habitual behaviour, checking updates frequently throughout the day (Donghee & Mousa, 2019). Social media also serves as a digital agora, where users can not only consume news but also share and discuss it with others. This indicates motivations related to social interaction, such as the desire to be part of conversations, to stay informed about topics of common interest, and to reinforce social connections. Furthermore, personalised notifications from news apps can trigger a sense of urgency or relevance, motivating users to consume news to stay informed about breaking events or topics they are interested in (Roy & Roy, 2024). The motivations for consuming news on social media include the desire for timely and convenient access to information, minimal cognitive effort, social sharing, and interaction, as well as personalised content delivery (Donghee & Mousa, 2019).

Motivations for news consumption on social media include the desire to be exposed to different perspectives, to access deeper background information on topics, and to get information directly from eyewitnesses (Roy & Roy, 2024). Many users appreciate the interactivity social media offers, such as participating in discussions and sharing their opinions with others. Additionally, social media may fulfill social needs, entertain, and provide a way to utilize spare

time (Whiting & Williams, 2013). Furthermore, the ease of accessing news on mobile devices through social media has led to habitual consumption patterns, due to the low cognitive effort required to read micro-news, which are short snippets of information often accompanied by links to full articles (Wohn & Ahmadi, 2019).

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative survey research design to examine the influence of social media assertiveness on news dissemination in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The population comprised students and staff of these higher educational institutions in the state, from which a representative sample was drawn using stratified and simple random sampling technique to ensure adequate representation across faculties and departments. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire designed to measure variables such as the level of exposure to social media, patterns of assertive communication, perceived credibility of disseminated news and audience reception. The instrument was validated through expert review and tested for reliability using a pilot study, while data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistical tools to determine the nature and extent of relationships between social media assertiveness and news dissemination within the selected institutions. The population of admitted students in Rivers State University is 23,200 (as gotten from ICTC), while the staff strength is 2,425. The population of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education students is 19,915 while the staff strength is 1,945 (University website 2025). The population was therefore $19,915+1,945+2,425+23,200=47,485$. These figures were gotten from the bursary departments of the two universities and they exclude the casual workers. The sample size for the study was 400 determined using Taro Yamane formula.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Extent members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Community use social media for news dissemination

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Σ	Mean	Remark
Members of my school community use social media for news dissemination	350 (1,400)	20 (60)	5 (10)	25 (25)	400	1,495	3.7	Agreed
Social media is a primary means of news dissemination in the school community	50 (200)	75 (225)	220 (440)	55 (55)	400	920	2.3	Disagreed
Members actively share news on social media platforms	100 (400)	150 (450)	100 (200)	50 (50)	400	1100	2.7	Agreed

The table shows a very strong consensus that members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use social media for news dissemination, with a high mean score of 3.7 indicating agreement. However, respondents disagreed (mean = 2.3) that social media is the *primary* means of news dissemination within the school community, suggesting that although it is widely used, it may not have completely displaced other channels such as official bulletins, websites, or face-to-face communication. Additionally, the agreement (mean = 2.7) that members actively share news on social media indicates moderate participation in news

circulation. This implies that social media functions as a significant but complementary channel for news dissemination rather than the dominant or exclusive source within the institutions.

Table 2: How social media impact the spread of news within the School Community

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Σ	Mean	Remark
Social media has a significant impact on the spread of news in Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education	340 (1,360)	20 (60)	8 (16)	32 (32)	400	1,468	3.7	Agreed
Social media speeds up news dissemination in the school community and increases the reach of news in the community	220 (880)	70 (210)	54 (108)	56 (56)	400	1,254	3.1	Agreed

The findings reveal a strong perception that social media significantly impacts the spread of news within the two institutions, with a high mean score of 3.7. Respondents also agreed (mean = 3.1) that social media accelerates news dissemination and increases its reach within the school community. This suggests that while social media may not be considered the primary source of news, it plays a crucial amplifying role by enhancing speed and audience penetration. The data therefore underscore the catalytic function of social media in expanding the visibility and immediacy of institutional information.

Table 3: Types of news most frequently shared on social media platforms by members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Community

Type of News	SA	A	D	SD	N	Σ	Mean	Remark
Local news is frequently shared on social media	345 (1,380)	20 (60)	5 (10)	30 (30)	400	1,480	3.8	Agreed
Entertainment news is frequently shared on social media	225 (900)	75 (225)	45 (90)	55 (55)	400	1,270	3.2	Agreed
Sports news is frequently shared on social media	30 (120)	50 (150)	200 (400)	120 (120)	400	790	1.9	Disagreed
Community events are frequently shared on social media	200 (800)	100 (300)	50 (100)	50 (50)	400	1,250	3.1	Agreed

The table indicates that local news (mean = 3.8) and community events (mean = 3.2) are the most frequently shared categories of news within the institutions, reflecting a strong interest in information directly affecting the school community. In contrast, respondents agreed that entertainment news (mean = 3.1) are frequently shared and with sports recording the lowest mean of 1.9. This suggests that social media usage within these academic communities is more

institution-centered rather than primarily recreational or sports-driven. The pattern highlights a preference for locally relevant and community-based content over general entertainment or sports updates.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: To what extent do members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use social media for news dissemination?

The findings indicate a strong consensus that members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education use social media for news dissemination (Mean = 3.7, Agreed as shown on table 1). This suggests that social media platforms constitute an important communication channel within the two institutions. The result aligns with evidence from the Pew Research Center (2021), which shows that a substantial proportion of adults rely on social media for accessing and sharing news. Within university environments, where digital literacy and connectivity are relatively high, such usage patterns are particularly pronounced.

However, respondents disagreed that social media is the *primary* means of news dissemination in the select schools (Mean = 2.3 on table 1). This implies that although widely used, social media does not completely replace traditional or official institutional channels such as notice boards, institutional websites, emails, or face-to-face communication. This finding reflects broader trends reported by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism (Newman et al., 2021), which indicate that digital platforms often complement rather than fully displace other news sources. Thus, social media functions as part of a hybrid communication ecosystem within the institutions.

Furthermore, the agreement that members actively share news on social media platforms as shown on table 1 (Mean = 2.7) highlights participatory engagement in the news dissemination process. This supports Kümpel, Karnowski, and Keyling's (2015) argument that user-driven sharing is central to how news circulates on social networks. In the context of these Rivers State institutions, members are not merely consumers of information but active disseminators, contributing to peer-to-peer diffusion of news across digital networks.

Research Question 2: How does social media impact the spread of news within the select school?

The data reveal strong agreement that social media has a significant impact on the spread of news within Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (Mean = 3.7; table 2). This underscores the perceived influence of digital platforms in shaping how information flows across the institutions. The Pew Research Center (2021) similarly reports that social media platforms play a crucial role in how news is encountered, discussed, and redistributed in contemporary society. Within academic communities, this impact may extend to academic updates, policy changes, and student-related announcements.

Respondents also agreed that social media speeds up news dissemination and increases the reach of news within the schools (Mean = 3.1). This aligns with findings from the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism Digital News Report (Newman et al., 2021), which emphasizes the immediacy and expansive reach of digital news networks. The interactive structure of social media enables rapid reposting, commenting, and amplification, thereby enhancing visibility beyond immediate physical boundaries.

These findings suggest that social media performs both a catalytic and amplificatory function within the institutions. Beyond merely serving as a communication tool, it significantly shapes the speed, circulation, and scale of news dissemination. As Vraga and Bode (2018) note, digital

platforms influence not only exposure to news but also engagement patterns, which may further intensify the spread of institutional information within these schools.

Research Question 3: What types of news are most frequently shared on social media platforms by members of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education?

The results show strong agreement that local news is frequently shared on social media (Mean = 3.8), indicating that institution-centered information dominates digital sharing practices. This is consistent with findings from the Pew Research Center (2021), which highlight that audiences tend to engage more actively with news that directly affects their immediate communities. In university contexts, such local news may include academic schedules, administrative updates, and campus developments.

Entertainment news was also agreed to be frequently shared (Mean = 3.2), suggesting that recreational and lifestyle-oriented content forms a noticeable part of social media interactions within the institutions. This aligns with patterns observed by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism (Newman et al., 2021), which indicate that entertainment content often attracts high engagement on digital platforms. The finding reflects the dual informational and social functions of social media in academic settings.

Conversely, respondents disagreed that sports news is frequently shared (Mean = 1.9), marking it as the least prominent category among the options presented. Meanwhile, community events were agreed to be frequently shared (Mean = 3.1), emphasizing the role of social media in promoting campus-based activities and collective participation. Overall, the pattern suggests that news sharing within these schools prioritizes locally relevant and socially engaging content over sports-related updates, reflecting a community-oriented digital communication culture.

Conclusion

This study examined social media use and its influence on news dissemination within Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The findings reveal that social media is widely used for news dissemination within the schools, with members actively engaging in the sharing of information. However, while social media plays a significant role, it is not regarded as the primary channel of news dissemination, indicating the continued relevance of traditional and official institutional communication platforms. The study further establishes that social media significantly impacts the spread of news by enhancing its speed, reach, and overall visibility within the academic environment.

In addition, the study demonstrates that the types of news most frequently shared are predominantly local and community-centered, alongside entertainment-related content, while sports news receives comparatively lower attention. This pattern reflects a communication culture that prioritizes institution-specific information and socially engaging content over other categories. Overall, the findings underscore the growing importance of social media as a complementary and influential tool in institutional news dissemination. The study therefore contributes to a clearer understanding of how digital communication dynamics shape information flow within cosmopolitan university communities in Rivers State and highlights the need for strategic management of social media to ensure accuracy, credibility and effective engagement.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education should maintain verified and actively managed social media accounts to ensure accurate, timely and credible dissemination of news while reducing misinformation.
2. The school authorities should link their social media pages directly with other traditional communication channels such as official websites, emails and notice boards to maximize reach and maintain reliability.
3. Regular digital literacy programs should be organized to educate students and staff on ethical news sharing, source verification and responsible use of social media.

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